

THE PROBLEM OF TIME AND HUMAN BEING IN THE STORIES OF ERKIN AZAM'S

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Abstract. *In the article, Erkin A'zam's stories reflect observations of the time and human problems. The characters of the stories "The Year of the Father's Birthday", "The Answer", "Days Other than the Holiday", their conflict situations with the social environment, and the inner feelings of the characters are shown with opposite examples.*

Keywords: *story, character, character, hero, conflict, solution, social environment, safura, journalistic work.*

INTRODUCTION

The need to research the place and national cultural heritage of the literary studies of the period of independence in the international arena, to understand the values, to go deeper into the essence of fiction in the process of today's globalization, to justify the worthy place of fiction works in the development of world literature, the heritage of creators who had a strong influence on the literature of the next era. is learning. The current reforms and ongoing processes in the cultural and educational spheres present a number of new tasks to Uzbek literary studies. "Today, we are moving on the path of innovative development aimed at radically renewing all spheres of state and community life. It's not for nothing, of course. Because in today's fast-paced world, who wins? The country that relies on a new idea, a new idea, and innovation will win." [1] In this process, the role and importance of the product of the artistic thinking of a particular nation in the elevation of the spiritual world of humanity is determined by its specific characteristics.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Any artistic work reflects some problems of its time, be it domestic, social, or political. Because the creator sees existence with his own eyes and writes his work based on his worldview, thinking, level of knowledge, feelings, and mood. "Of course, literature should highlight the current problems of its time. With this, he draws people's attention to a certain issue," [7;49] says Professor Abdulla Ulug'ov.

If we look at the literature of the world, we can witness that, regardless of the topic, the famous works of art shed light on the problems of the time. We see this situation in our literature as well. For example, if we look at the example of "Otkan Kunlar" or "Night and Day" novels, both works served to reflect the actual issue of their time. Perhaps for this reason, it is still not losing its place on the bookshelves.

RESULTS

In most of Erkin A'zam's works, the people of our time are depicted in conflict with the social environment, in the vortex of periodic problems. The cases described above are described in the question of whether we can get the stories and journalistic works created by the writer. In the novel "Shovqin" great social reality, political and spiritual crises were written. Most of E.Azam's short stories, which we took as the object of our research, reflected the problems of the time and people.

Speaking about the writer's book "Paradise is the rule", doctor of philology, professor Umarali Normatov expresses his thoughts on this matter as follows: "All the works included in the book are the world of our days, the fate of people - contemporaries. , discusses life and life problems that torment them. The period of transition from one system to another will be unfolded in front of your eyes with the total contradictions, positive and negative sides, obstacles and pains of evolution, changes occurring in the nature, views, destiny, mentality of contemporaries. [6;4] In his first story, the writer focuses on the problems of the era and man. The hero of the play, the young student Askar Shodibekov, has a conflict with the people of his time and social environment.

In this work, which is called Shartaki's story, a series of images of people with different characters have been created. This story, built on the basis of the hero's speech, includes Askar, Rakhmatilla, Akhmadkhanov, Akbarova, as well as a number of episodic characters.

Ramatilla acts according to the situation, Akhmadkhanov, a teacher of literary history, is an "expert" on the birth years of poets and writers, Akbarova is one of the "modern" girls more prone to rumors and gossip - her activity and activity it takes place within this framework. The story is told in the language of Askar, who is also not an "angel". Shartaki, obstinate, the kind of people who talk to your face. In this work, which is taken from the life of the students, Askar gets into many dangerous situations because of this verb.

"To his uncle who kicked his wife out of the house along with his five children:

- Now find a pair of binoculars, hang them around your neck, and watch the young and old girls pass by, - he innocently instructed;

To the teacher who asked why he was not recording the lecture:

"I'm not used to copying the sentences in the textbook," he stammered.

Who is this?" [4;7]

The writer does not "see" a smooth life path for his characters. Life

The essence of the characters is revealed depending on the situation they fall into. People of stable character get out of this life's eddies, although not easily. And those who are easily influenced by the transient environment, leave their beliefs to the vortex.

Erkin A'zam's characters are not depicted in the context of very large social issues, but against the background of everyday worries and ups and downs. Here is the description given to Nuriddin Elchiyev, the hero of the story "Answer":

"A person like Elchiyev can be found everywhere, in every office. They don't stand out and say yes at meetings and meetings, they don't have a decisive vote, they just raise their hands or clap their hands when necessary. We rarely mention such things even during the holidays and when some light touches the distribution. But everyone can't imagine without them: public scenes need people! In difficult situations, especially when someone is worried, we immediately look for them: selfless, grateful, reliable. Some may not be seen in the office for weeks, but if he is absent for an hour, it is immediately known - there is a place, a place! You are humble, poor, but you have a place that no one else can occupy, no one else deserves!" [4 ;70]

People like Elchiyev, who are confused by their life and work, are shown in the words of the writer, "broken, exploded, exploded from the inside".

Nuriddin Elchiyev is a broad verb by nature, someone's pain and joy "universal" person who accepts everyone as his own, gets along with everyone, big or small. He is kind to those around him, a friend, an exemplary father in the family, the head of the family, a kind person. Such a person commits suicide from the dabdurist! That's the crux of the story.

As he does not know how to complain about his marriage, he does not expect any miracle from him, it is unusual for a person who is used to living with gratitude for all his luck to suddenly commit suicide. Why? Why is Elchiyev lying in the hospital? why what for? seeks answers to "The earth splits open and penetrates" from his actions. Nuriddin Elchiyev sums up his life path while reminiscing: how did he live?, why did he live?, do what he calls intentions and goals have any significance in the world of life?

The hero questions himself. But a good response to his actions can't find. There are mysteries of the human psyche that are difficult to explain with words and thoughts. The writer confronts his hero with these puzzles.

DISCUSSION

It is worth mentioning another feature of Erkin Azam's works, the author does not lead the reader to ready conclusions in any of his works. It is up to Nuriddin Elchiyev, as well as the reader, to come to a certain solution, as in the story "The Answer". In other words, the writer does not lead his hero through the paths of life, but the hero who is led by life itself observes his behavior and mentality.

A person can endure all life's blows with patience, but a trivial excuse and reason can throw him out of balance. This is the situation that Elchiyev found himself in. Maybe the blows of life have gradually weakened Elchiyev, and what if that seemingly trivial excuse and reason was the last, decisive blow?

Bakir, the hero of Erkin Azam's next short story "Days other than Eid", was born and raised in a simple, low-income family. The environment does not support such a mess. Bakir was humble, quiet, learned to work and was brought up in the spirit of Uzbek traditions. But he married for love. Bargida's family environment is the complete opposite of Bakir's family. They have completely free concepts of morality, relationships, behavior, and family responsibility. Bakir is condemned to live in the environment of these two families. The feelings that he considers sacred, after entering the second environment, become like habits left over from a mere pastime. Bakir Bargidalar and his environment: parents, sister, pooch, Safura and others try to get out of the spider's web. But it's too late, freedom, free will, you have to endure it, life is about patience. But until when?

What kind of character does Bakir have in "Days other than the holiday"? Is his character strong or weak? Bakir is cheerful and anxious by nature. However, there is no room for complacency and concern in the environment in which he finds himself (at work, in the family). Therefore, the determination in his character is not noticeable. Lies, fake, insincere relationships that are on the tip of the tongue lead him to "fry in his own oil", he becomes mentally isolated, he tries to get out of the invisible shackles of the environment. He doesn't have the will to get out of the situation he's in, but he doesn't want to stay in it either. The frivolous life in Bargida and his family, Chinnibek's hypocrisy, his pooch's mental disorder, Ukkiboyev's extortion (at work), alienation from his brothers and sisters (from his own family) put him in mental torture and unanswerable questions. He searches for his identity in the process.

The writer leaves the finale open, it is a reference to the reader, and the rest to Bakir.

It should be noted that leaving the conclusion open is also characteristic of other works of the writer. The writer does not bring the reader to a ready conclusion in any of his works.

CONCLUSION

In short, the writing period, changes related to the environment examines the psyche of the hero. Compares yesterday with today. In the works of Erkin A'zam, such characters are depicted with all their fullness and complexity.

Erkin A'zam's works cannot be imagined without sarcastic remarks, sarcasm and sarcasm. Khurshid Davron says, "When I start reading Erkin Aka's stories, I see his serious face and hand holding a pen." Each reader will find himself, his friend, brother, sister, neighbor among various characters. They move in a familiar environment in some cases, and in other cases in a foreign environment.

Erkin A'zam's works are distinguished by their unique humorous narrative style, sarcastic language, and unexpected artistic solutions. The fact that the writer reflects the most complicated aspects of a person through gestures, without showing them openly, increases the effectiveness of his works. Erkin A'zam created artistic characters in his stories and stories that are simple and simple, unlike others, clearly distinguished by their pains, worries, and personal experiences. Elucidating the philosophy of characters, methodological tension, strength of psychological analysis, building the plot of the work on the basis of characters, expressing the connection between events through images and details, the closeness of the speech of the author and the character, the commonality of psychologism and philosophy are the main features of Erkin A'zam's artistic style.

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